

From Pheromones to Policies: Reinforcement Learning for Engineered Biological Swarms

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Abstract. Swarm intelligence emerges from simple local interactions. We show a formal equivalence between pheromone-mediated aggregation in *C. elegans* and reinforcement learning: stigmergic signals implement distributed rewards and cross-learning updates. Using a foraging model grounded in empirical data, we reproduce *C. elegans* patch-selection in static environments. In dynamic settings, persistent pheromones create positive feedback that hinders adaptation by locking swarms to outdated sites. Computational bandit experiments reveal that implementing heterogeneity through a minority of exploratory, pheromone-insensitive agents restores plasticity and enables rapid task switching. Thus, behavioural heterogeneity balances exploration-exploitation and implements swarm-level extinction of obsolete strategies. Our results reinterpret stigmergy as externalised memory for collective credit assignment and link synthetic biology with RL-driven swarm control, pointing to programmable living systems capable of resilient decision-making.

1 Introduction

Collective animal behaviour illustrates how large groups accomplish sensing, decision making and actuation that far exceed the cognitive or energetic capacity of the individuals that compose them. These examples have inspired swarm intelligence, a biologically inspired, self-organised and decentralised problem-solving paradigm in which simple agents encode local interaction rules, enabling the collective to exhibit coherent and adaptive behaviour without any agent possessing global knowledge or acting as a central controller.

In artificial intelligence a parallel idea appears at the level of a single agent. Reinforcement learning (RL), as conceptualised by Sutton and Barto [14], synthesises psychological principles of Thorndike’s law of effect (trial-and-error learning), optimal control theory from engineering, and operant conditioning paradigms. Thus, what swarms exhibit at the population level and what a single RL agent exhibits at the individual level are two scales of the same cognitive learning dynamic: decentralised, incremental hypothesis testing driven by feedback from the environment. A direct consequence of treating learning as continual model revision

is adaptability (i.e., the capacity to maintain competent behaviour under changing conditions). In animal conditioning, extinction denotes the decay of a conditioned response when reinforcement ceases. Balancing knowledge consolidation and extinction [11], therefore amounts to regulating exploration–exploitation [17]. Achieving that balance is central to designing swarm systems that remain resilient, sample-efficient, and cognitively coherent over long horizons. For instance, theoretical models have shown that heterogeneity enhances optimal decision-making [3].

Even if swarm robotics shows promising engineering solutions, it falls short in facing natural environments [7]. This gap motivates the exploration of biological animal robots [4], where living organisms themselves constitute the agents. In this context, *Caenorhabditis elegans* (*C. elegans*) with its fully mapped neural connectome consisting of 302 neurons [16] emerges as a favorable candidate. This neural simplicity, combined with emerging techniques in neuro-synthetic biology [12], opens opportunities for creating bioengineered *C. elegans* as swarm agents. By genetically manipulating synaptic connectivity [13] and constructing in vivo gene circuits [9], it may become feasible to systematically alter collective behaviours, thus transforming *C. elegans* populations into a programmable biological swarm of robots.

C. elegans occurs in diverse natural and laboratory strains that span a behavioural continuum. The canonical laboratory reference strain *N2* has been demonstrated to be almost entirely *solitary*, whereas strains carrying the low-activity allele of the neuropeptide-receptor gene *npr-1* adopt a more *social* collective behaviour, i.e., clustering in clumps at the food interface [5]. Nonetheless, even these *social* worms exhibit little beyond simple aggregation, far from the elaborate tasks of eusocial or subsocial insects [2]. It is conceivable, however, that pheromone-based communication could be harnessed to engineer much more elaborate collective behaviour [1], allowing us to treat *C. elegans* populations as programmable biological robots whose coordination is mediated by tunable chemical signals.

Our study forges a formal bridge between engineered stigmergy (i.e., coordination via environmentally deposited pheromones) and RL, and examines how environmental volatility and population heterogeneity shape swarm adaptability in pheromone-guided foraging. We show the equivalence between pheromone-driven swarming dynamics and the Cross Learning update rule (validated against published in-vivo data), quantify the consensus–adaptability trade-off under environmental shifts, and demonstrate that a minority of exploration-oriented individuals sustains plasticity by enabling swarm-level extinction.

2 Model

We develop our model based on the empirical framework described in [10], with the aim of integrating pheromone-based communication into a swarm of *C. elegans*.

The intrinsic attractiveness of a food patch i with bacterial density D_i is given by the sigmoidal function

$$A_i = \sqrt{H} \frac{1 + 4 \left(\frac{D_i}{D_{\text{attract}}} \right)^k}{H + 4 \left(\frac{D_i}{D_{\text{attract}}} \right)^k}, \quad (1)$$

where bacterial attractiveness A_i is time-invariant and H controls the dynamic range, k the steepness of the response, and D_{attract} the characteristic density.

To model stigmergic reinforcement, we define the pheromone-induced modulation of patch attractiveness as

$$B_i(t) = 1 + \tau_i(t), \quad (2)$$

where $\tau_i(t)$ denotes the amount of pheromone present at site i at time t . Thus, pheromones linearly amplify the intrinsic attractiveness of a patch. Although pheromone sensing can be nonlinear and context-dependent [6], we adopt this linear formulation for analytical tractability.

The probability of worms aggregating at the i^{th} food patch, in an environment with M patches, is then given by

$$P_i(t) = \frac{B_i(t) A_i}{\sum_{j=1}^M B_j(t) A_j}. \quad (3)$$

We now characterise the temporal evolution of pheromone concentration. The quantity of pheromone at patch i evolves according to

$$\tau_i(t+1) = \rho \tau_i(t) + \Delta_{k,i}(t), \quad (4)$$

where the deposition term depends on individual decisions:

$$\Delta_{k,i}(t) = \begin{cases} Q, & \text{if agent } k \text{ selects patch } i, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Here, $0 \leq \rho \leq 1$ denotes the pheromone persistence rate, and $Q \geq 0$ is the amount of pheromone deposited upon selecting a patch. Together, these dynamics capture how local decisions reinforce patch attractiveness over time, driving collective aggregation through positive stigmergy.

3 Learning

In a multi-armed bandit with M actions, an agent maintains a policy $\pi(t) = (\pi_1(t), \dots, \pi_M(t))$, where $\pi_i(t)$ denotes the probability of selecting action i at time t . After selecting action k and receiving reward r_k , the policy is updated as

$$\pi_i(t+1) = \pi_i(t) + \alpha r_k \begin{cases} 1 - \pi_i(t), & \text{if } i = k, \\ -\pi_i(t), & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

where α is the learning rate.

We now establish how pheromone-mediated aggregation induces a reinforcement-learning update of patch-selection probabilities when agents (worms) act sequentially.

At time t , the probability of selecting patch i is given by Eq. 3. When a worm selects patch k at time t , it deposits pheromone Q at that site, yielding $\tau_k(t+1) = \rho \tau_k(t) + Q$, while pheromones at all other sites decay as $\tau_i(t+1) = \rho \tau_i(t)$.

Substituting these dynamics into the expression of $P_i(t+1)$ and regrouping the chosen and unchosen cases (derivations in the Supplement [15]) yields the update rule:

$$P_i(t+1) = P_i(t) + QR_k(t) \begin{cases} 1 - P_i(t), & \text{if } i = k, \\ -P_i(t), & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

with

$$R_k(t) = \frac{A_k}{\rho \sum_{j=1}^M \tau_j(t) A_j + QA_k}. \quad (8)$$

Eq. 7 is mathematically equivalent to the Cross Learning update (Eq. 6), where the reward signal is implicitly implemented through environmental stigmergy. In this interpretation, pheromone deposition acts as a distributed reinforcement mechanism, and the population distribution across patches corresponds to the agent’s policy.

This mechanism explains how local decisions can give rise to collective learning: actions that lead to higher bacterial payoff leave stronger pheromone traces, which bias subsequent choices and drive convergence toward optimal sites. However, purely positive feedback also induces a risk of lock-in under changing conditions, as persistent pheromones slow the extinction of outdated collective preferences. High pheromone persistence therefore hinders adaptation unless mechanisms promoting exploration are introduced.

Although worms act sequentially in our formulation, the equivalence holds at the population level due to the ergodicity of cross-learning dynamics, ensuring statistical equivalence with parallel updates. In simulations, pheromone accumulation is implemented via a finite replay buffer that approximates the total pheromone mass $\sum_j \tau_j(t)$.

4 Results

We present three types of experiments using the reinforcement learning model. The first experiment aims to validate our model, while the other two focus on the swarm’s response in dynamic environments.

4.1 Model Validation in Static Environment

We evaluate the model in a stateless multi-armed bandit and in a two-state bandit where rewards have Gaussian noise $\sigma = 0.1$ and are permuted at epoch $T = \Delta$. We initialise the policy with $\pi_1 = 0.9$ and $\pi_i = \frac{0.1}{M-1}$ for $i \geq 2$.

Fig. 1. Proportion of worms at each food patch over time. Solid lines: experimental mean over 58 videos (299 worms total); shaded: 95% bootstrap CI; dashed: model. Patch optical densities are $D \in \{0.2, 0.1, 0.05, 0.025\}$, respectively blue, purple, pink and orange ; an additional curve represents the proportion of worms outside patches in grey.

To validate our model, we compare its predictions with empirical data gathered from controlled experiments in [10]. In these experiments, four food patches were arranged in a square at 1.2 cm from the center of a plate. Each patch contained *E. coli OP50* at distinct densities: 0.2, 0.1, 0.05, and 0.025 (measured as Optical Density). In each trial, worms were placed in the center of the plate, and their distribution across patches was recorded over 7200 seconds. We compared the results of the experiment with the prediction of our model in the multi-armed stateless bandit setting.

Figure 1 displays the average time evolution of the proportion of worms present in each patch as well as those outside the patches, approximating an Ideal Free Distribution (IDF) [8].

We found the best-fit parameters using Differential Evolution (DE). The parameters found for the Attractiveness sigmoid function are: $H = 51.5, k = 0.29, D_{attract} = 0.003$. The pheromone secretion parameter (i.e., the learning rate) of the model was also adjusted to best fit the data, therefore Q was set to 0.02. With these parameters, our model achieved an MSE of $2.595E-2$.

4.2 Adaptation to Dynamic Environments

To investigate the swarm’s adaptability under changing conditions, we consider a dynamic environment in which patch attractiveness changes abruptly at time $t = \Delta$.

Before the switch ($t < \Delta$), the environment is in its first state: arm a_1 has attractiveness $r_1 = 0$, arm a_2 has attractiveness $r_2 = A(D = 1) = 2.22$, and arm a_3 has attractiveness $r_3 = 0$.

At time $t = \Delta$, the environment transitions to a second state. In this new state, arm a_1 remains non-rewarding ($r_1 = 0$), arm a_2 becomes non-

Fig. 2. Adaptation dynamics in a dynamic three-arm two-state bandit task. (A) Policy evolution in a homogeneous population. (B) Policy evolution in a heterogeneous population with a fraction $\epsilon = 0.1$ of exploratory individuals that ignore pheromones. In (A–B), both populations operate in a two-state multi-armed bandit with three arms, start fully distributed on a_1 , aggregate at a_2 , and experience an environmental switch at epoch $\Delta = 100$ (red vertical line), after which a_3 becomes the only rewarding option. (C) Mean Time to Adapt (MTA) in the same task. The swarm plot shows MTA as a function of pheromone memory (black line: mean over 5 runs, 1000 epochs). Heatmaps report MTA across exploratory fraction $\epsilon \in \{0.001, 0.01, 0.05, 0.1, 0.2\}$ (x-axis) and switch time $\Delta \in \{50, 100, 150, 200, 300\}$ (y-axis).

rewarding ($r_2 = 0$), and arm a_3 becomes the only attractive option, with $r_3 = A(D = 1) = 2.22$.

Using this setup with $\Delta = 100$, *Memory size* = 350 (i.e., Buffer size), maximum number of epochs $T = 500$, and number of runs $N = 100$, we first examined a homogeneous population. In Figure 2A–B, we show the evolution of the policy across arms. In the homogeneous case (Figure 2A), 13% of the runs successfully aggregated at the new spot after the state change. This limited success arises from the swarm’s strong positive stigmergic reinforcement: the continuous deposition of pheromones sustains a positive feedback loop that can trap the swarm at the first

spot, even after its attractiveness has dropped to zero. We therefore introduce a fraction ϵ of exploratory individuals that ignore pheromones and rely solely on bacterial attractiveness.

In the heterogeneous population, we assume that $1 - \epsilon$ of the *C. elegans* can both sense and secrete pheromones, while ϵ are blind to pheromones but still secrete them. Hence, the exploratory group relies solely on bacterial density for navigation. Figure 2B shows that introducing $\epsilon = 0.1$ exploratory individuals leads to a 100% success rate in reaching and aggregating at the final spot. These findings highlight the importance of exploratory agents in avoiding local attractor traps created by purely attractive pheromone-driven learning.

We quantify the swarm’s response to an environmental switch using the Mean Time to Adapt (MTA):

$$\text{MTA} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \min\{k \geq 0 : \pi_3(\Delta + k) \geq 0.9\}, \quad (9)$$

If the threshold is not reached before the terminal time T , the adaptation time is set to $T - \Delta$.

Figure 2C summarises adaptation as a function of pheromone memory, switch time Δ , and exploratory fraction ϵ . Larger memory increases lock-in and requires larger ϵ to recover fast switching, whereas short memory yields consistently low MTA across Δ and ϵ .

5 Conclusion

We presented a framework linking pheromone-mediated coordination and RL. By deriving an update rule equivalent to cross-learning, we showed that positive stigmergy acts as an implicit reward, turning collective aggregation into distributed learning where the environment stores reinforcement history.

This shared feedback structure explains efficient convergence in static environments and lock-in in dynamic ones unless exploration and extinction mechanisms are present. We showed that a small fraction of exploratory, pheromone-insensitive individuals restores flexibility, enabling the swarm to revise outdated strategies.

Overall, our results bridge biological learning, swarm dynamics, and RL, and provide design principles for programmable biohybrid collectives capable of adaptive behaviour in volatile environments.

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